

USING COMMUNICATIVE GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: Communicative games have become a successful technique in teaching English language in order to increase learner effectiveness and engagement in the lessons. These interactive and entertaining games provide a dynamic way to practise language skills. In this article, we discuss the advantages of teaching English through communicative games.

Key words: communicative games, technique, interactive, teaching English.

Аннотация: Коммуникативные игры стали успешной методикой обучения английскому языку, чтобы повысить эффективность и вовлеченность учащихся в уроки. Эти интерактивные и развлекательные игры предоставляют динамичный способ практиковать языковые навыки. В этой статье мы обсуждаем преимущества обучения английскому языку с помощью коммуникативных игр.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативные игры, методика, интерактивный, обучение английскому языку.

Annotatsiya: Ingliz tili o'qitishda kommunikativ o'yinlar o'quvchilarning darslarda faolligi va qiziqishini oshirishga qaratilgan eng samarali metodga aylandi. Bu interaktiv va qiziqarli o'yinlar til ko'nikmalarini dinamik usulda mashq qilishga qaratilgan. Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini kommunikativ o'yinlar yordamida o'rgatishning afzalliklarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ o'yinlar, texnika, interaktiv, ingliz tilini o'qitish.

Communicative games are intended to encourage the practical use of language by emphasising real-life communication in the lessons. These games frequently include role-playing, problem-solving, and collaborative activities that enable students to use English in various situations. According to Larsen-Freeman (2000), communicative games provide interaction between language learners. Students practise a variety of language skills through communicative activities, such as speaking, listening, and vocabulary. For example, role-playing games force learners to speak English in context, which improves fluency and conversational abilities. According to Nation (2013), such interactive exercises allow learners to use language in ways that strengthen their understanding and retention.

In order to effectively incorporate communicative games into English teaching, teachers should choose games that meet with the learning objectives and proficiency levels of the students. For instance, simple vocabulary games are suitable for beginners, while more complex role-playing activities may be appropriate for advanced learners. According to Ur (1996), the selection of games should be based on their relevance to the lesson content and the specific needs of the learners. Additionally, teachers can establish a classroom environment that encourages communication.

Sigurðardóttir (2010) classified games into the following categories: games for dividing larger groups into smaller groups, introduction games, group games, physical games, scavenger hunt games, educational games, theoretical expression games, drawing and colouring games, educational card games, word games, story games, and question games. Also, games can be divided into cooperative and competitive games. Cooperative games, which

centre around teamwork to achieve a common objective, can be a great approach to develop the skill of working with others, even though competitive games can be a helpful way to get some students' interest and keep them focused. Since winning and losing are not the focus of cooperative games, no one should have to experience damage to their self-confidence, which could improve learning outcomes.

"Walking the line" is an example of a physical game in which participants must walk a line while performing various types of duties, such as walking backwards or balancing a book on their heads. To make this game more appropriate for a language school, the teacher should deliver the directions in the target language, such as "everybody has to walk backwards". Another example of a physical game is the game "Simon says," in which one person plays Simon and gives the other players directions such as "jump" or "clap your hands." I classify this game as a physical game because Simon's directives are typically physical.

Activities such as "Simon Says" are part of a teaching method known as Total Physical Response (TPR), which teaches languages by enabling learners to observe and take their time understanding the language before having to speak it. TPR is regarded to be an effective way of teaching a foreign language for two reasons. The first is that it is thought to reduce the stress level of learning a language, making it more enjoyable; the second is that it is similar to how children learn their native language, where they are exposed to the language for many months before beginning to speak.

Some games require theoretical expressions. For example, "Who Am I?" is a game that requires theoretical expression. In this activity, the class is typically split into two teams. Next, individual students take the stage in front of the class and role-play a particular profession that the teacher has assigned them. Teams alternately make guesses and pose questions, with the actor limited to provide a yes or no response. The scoring can then be set up so that a team asking a question gets one point if the answer is repeated in the affirmative, and the team that identifies the actor playing the role gets five points.

"To Tell a Story" is a story game. The participants sit in a circle, and one of them is assigned the job of storyteller. The teacher whispers one phrase in each student's ear and asks him or her to memorise it. The storyteller then begins narrating a story, pausing occasionally to point at a student, who must then recite the phrase whispered to him by the teacher. The storyteller must then incorporate this term into the story, which generally results in humorous repercussions. This game is ideal for language instruction because both the tale and the vocabulary are in the target language.

To sum up, communicative games are an important pedagogical technique in English language teaching which provide with several benefits that go beyond standard methods. These games help to improve engagement, language skills, and social and cognitive development, making learning more effective and entertaining. Teachers that incorporate communicative games into their teaching methods can foster a dynamic and engaged classroom atmosphere that assists students' language acquisition and overall growth in the target language.

References:

1. Larsen-Freeman, D. (2000). *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. Oxford

University Press.

2. Lee, J. (2016). *The Impact of Communicative Games on Language Learning*. TESOL Journal, 7(2), 45-60.
3. Nation, I. S. P. (2013). *Learning Vocabulary in Another Language*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Sigurðardóttir, S. D. (2010). *The use of games in the language classroom* (Doctoral dissertation).
5. Ur, P. (1996). *A Course in Language Teaching: Practice and Theory*. Cambridge University Press.